

Automated Distributed Ledger Infrastructure for Continuous Cybersecurity Certification in Multi-Stakeholder Environments

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Abstract—Continuous cybersecurity certification requires multiple independent stakeholders, such as manufacturers, operators, and certification authorities, to exchange and verify security evidence across organizational boundaries without depending on a centralized trust authority. Maintaining the integrity, provenance, and controlled disclosure of heterogeneous certification artifacts (including software and hardware bills of materials, compliance reports, and vulnerability records) in such multi-party settings remains an open challenge.

This paper addresses this challenge within the COBALT project by designing and deploying a permissioned distributed ledger infrastructure based on Hyperledger Fabric. The proposed system employs a multi-channel architecture that enforces data sovereignty among stakeholders, while a hash-on-chain anchoring pattern ensures that only cryptographic proofs are committed to the ledger, keeping raw evidence under each party’s control. To overcome the well-documented operational complexity of Fabric, we contribute an infrastructure-as-code framework that derives a complete network, including its cryptographic material, channel configuration, and chaincode lifecycle, from a small set of declarative JSON specifications, reducing deployment from hours to minutes.

Experimental validation in the COBALT testbed confirms the functional correctness of the evidence anchoring workflow and demonstrates that the containerized infrastructure operates within modest resource constraints, providing a reusable foundation for distributed trust in certification ecosystems.

Index Terms—Hyperledger Fabric, Infrastructure-as-Code, Continuous Certification, Distributed Trust, Multi-Stakeholder

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid digitalization of critical infrastructures and the interconnection of supply chains have exposed a significant gap between the operational reality of ICT systems and their security certification status. Traditional certification schemes rely on static, point-in-time evaluations that remain valid for years, yet in the era of development and operations (DevOps), microservices, and rapid threat evolution, a system certified today may become vulnerable tomorrow due to a new zero-day exploit or a configuration drift.

To address this challenge, the European Union (EU) has established a robust regulatory framework. The Cybersecurity

Act (CSA) introduced the European Cybersecurity Certification Framework to harmonize schemes across Member States [2], while the Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) mandates security across the entire product lifecycle, requiring active vulnerability management and rapid remediation [1]. While the legal mandate for continuous assurance is clear, the technical means to implement it remain fragmented. Complying with these regulations through manual audit procedures is administratively unfeasible and prone to error.

This continuous certification model involves multiple independent stakeholders (manufacturers, certification authorities and operators) who must exchange and validate security evidence without relying on a single trusted intermediary for integrity verification. Evidence must flow between mutually untrusting parties, and no single entity should control the consensus and anchoring infrastructure, as this creates both a single point of failure and potential conflicts of interest. To address this problem, the COBALT framework proposes a decentralized platform that automates the continuous certification of ICT products, integrating monitoring, assessment, and decision-making components with a Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) infrastructure based on Hyperledger Fabric.

This paper presents the design and implementation of the distributed trust layer within COBALT, focusing on three main contributions:

- 1) An automated infrastructure-as-code system that transforms declarative JSON specifications into fully operational Hyperledger Fabric networks, reducing deployment time from hours to minutes.
- 2) A privacy-preserving multi-channel architecture that enforces data sovereignty among certification stakeholders through segregated ledgers and a hash-on-chain anchoring pattern.
- 3) A complete integration layer that bridges the COBALT ecosystem with the permissioned ledger through federated identity mapping and a REST API gateway.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews related work on certification evidence man-

agement and blockchain deployment automation. Section III introduces the COBALT framework and motivates the need for a distributed trust layer. Section IV describes the architecture and design principles of the automated deployment system. Section V details the implementation and smart contract design. Section VI presents validation results, and Section VII concludes with future work.

II. RELATED WORK

Blockchain technology has gained traction as a foundation for distributed trust in multi-stakeholder certification ecosystems. Neisse *et al.* [4] proposed a seminal interledger-based framework under the EU Cybersecurity Act, demonstrating how multiple permissioned ledgers could be interconnected to provide transparency, accountability, and cross-border security assurance without reliance on a single authority. Their architecture established a logical model in which blockchain networks serve as shared sources of truth among independent parties. However, this work, like most subsequent blockchain-based trust architectures, assumes an operational network is already in place and does not address the practical effort required to bootstrap and maintain it across organizational boundaries.

Deploying a Hyperledger Fabric network remains a complex and error-prone undertaking. The process requires coordinating PKI setup, MSP configuration, channel creation, and chaincode deployment across all consortium members in a strictly ordered sequence. Tran *et al.* [5] characterize this process as “time-consuming, error-prone, and dependent on platform-specific knowledge,” noting that deployment difficulty grows combinatorially as the number of organizations and configuration parameters increases. Even experienced practitioners acknowledge that Fabric “has many configuration possibilities, but is very complex and has a high entry barrier” [6]. Compared to public blockchains where any participant can join by running a node, permissioned ledgers like Fabric impose a significantly higher entry barrier that demands careful orchestration.

Several tools attempt to mitigate this complexity. Hyperledger *Cello* [8] offers blockchain-as-a-service provisioning, while lightweight toolkits such as *Minifabric* [9] and *Fablo* [10] enable rapid deployment of basic networks with minimal configuration. More advanced platforms like *HFabD+M* [6] provide web-based interfaces for specifying topologies and managing the chaincode lifecycle, reporting significant reductions in manual effort. Despite these advances, existing solutions focus on automating the *mechanics* of deployment for static topologies; none allow operators to declaratively specify trust relationships and governance policies at a high level and have the system configure the network accordingly. Our work bridges this gap by enabling developers to define consortium networks in a declarative, trust-aware manner that the system deploys and maintains automatically.

III. THE COBALT FRAMEWORK

COBALT is a European Horizon Europe project that proposes a decentralized platform for the automated continuous certification of ICT products. Its architecture transitions from traditional static evaluation models towards a distributed, dynamic, and automated ecosystem aligned with the CSA, CRA, and Network and Information Security Directive (NIS2) regulatory frameworks [1]–[3]. The platform integrates Security Digital Twins for non-intrusive monitoring, automated risk assessment, and a permissioned DLT infrastructure to establish a continuous and verifiable root of trust.

A. Architectural Overview

The COBALT architecture is structured into four logical layers (see Fig. 1). The *Operations Layer* abstracts the Target of Evaluation (ToE) through a Security Digital Twin that maintains a live replica of security-critical attributes, enabling non-disruptive auditing without impacting the operational system. The *Assessment Layer* transforms raw telemetry into risk insights: specialized Evidence Collectors normalize data into a Common Certification Model (CCM), and conformity assessment modules evaluate this evidence against certification scheme rules to produce compliance reports and risk scores.

Fig. 1. COBALT layered architecture.

The *Management Layer* coordinates the overall workflow. The Orchestrator routes evidence through the assessment pipeline, while the CCM Manager acts as the repository and API gateway for certification artifacts. The Decision Engine autonomously triggers lifecycle actions (e.g., certificate suspension) when risk thresholds are breached. The critical service-to-service communications are secured through a centralized Identity Manager. The evidence handled by COBALT is structured using OSCAL [11], a National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) standard that provides machine-

readable formats for representing security control assessments, enabling interoperability across the certification ecosystem.

B. The Need for a Distributed Trust Layer

The certification process involves three independent stakeholders: Manufacturers, who submit design-time artifacts such as SBOMs and HBOMs; Conformity Assessment Bodies (CABs), who validate compliance and issue certificates; and Operators, who collect runtime evidence from deployed systems. These parties must exchange and verify certification artifacts without relying on a centralized authority, as no single entity should control the integrity verification infrastructure.

The *Distributed Trust Layer*, built upon Hyperledger Fabric, addresses this requirement. Its permissioned nature ensures that every transaction is cryptographically attributable to a known entity, which is indispensable for non-repudiation and regulatory accountability. Unlike public blockchains, Fabric’s channel capability enables logical data segregation, allowing stakeholders to share a common infrastructure while keeping sensitive intellectual property and operational telemetry isolated. The ledger does not store raw evidence but acts as a cryptographic anchoring layer: only hashes of certification artifacts are committed on-chain, preserving data sovereignty while providing tamper-proof audit trails. However, deploying and managing such multi-organization Fabric networks remains operationally complex, which motivates the automated deployment system described in the following sections.

IV. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE AND DESIGN

This section details the architectural design of the automated deployment system, which addresses the operational complexity of Hyperledger Fabric through declarative abstractions, dynamic cryptographic provisioning, and decoupled identity management.

A. Design Principles for Automated Fabric Deployment

Hyperledger Fabric’s permissioned model relies on a complex PKI and MSP architecture to ensure accountability [7]. To mitigate configuration errors inherent in manual deployments, our system introduces a high-level abstraction layer based on three core principles.

1) *Declarative Network Specification*: Rather than managing dozens of interdependent YAML configuration files (`configtx`, `docker-compose`, connection profiles), our system derives the entire network topology from three concise JSON specifications:

- `organizations.json`: defines the participating domains and their distinct roles.
- `channels.json`: maps channel names to member organizations, encoding the network’s trust boundaries.
- `chaincodes.json`: specifies smart contract source paths, versions, and target channels.

This model separates the *intent* (the high-level trust topology) from the *mechanics* of deployment, allowing the automation engine to determine how to realize the specification technically.

2) *Automated Infrastructure Provisioning*: The system programmatically provisions the complete network infrastructure in a strictly ordered sequence:

- 1) **PKI Generation**. The system deploys a dedicated Fabric certificate authority (CA) server for each organization and programmatically interacts with it via the `fabric-ca-client` to register and enroll administrators, peer nodes, and orderers. This produces the full certificate hierarchy (Root CA, TLS, and signing keys) for all network participants, automatically organizing the generated material into the required MSP directory structure.
- 2) **Configuration Artifacts**. By iterating over the JSON definitions, the system generates a synchronized `configtx.yaml`. It then executes `configtxgen` to create the genesis block, channel creation transactions, and anchor peer updates, ensuring that MSP definitions match the generated cryptographic material.
- 3) **Container Orchestration**. Finally, the script generates tailored Docker Compose files. It configures peer nodes, CAs, orderers, and CouchDB instances with the correct volume mounts and environment variables, connecting them to a shared container network to enable service discovery by hostname.

3) *Lifecycle and Chaincode Automation*: The system automates the decentralized governance workflows required by Fabric 2.x. It manages the idempotent joining of peers to their assigned channels and handles the full chaincode lifecycle: compiling Java sources via Gradle, installing packages on target peers, collecting organizational approvals, and committing the chaincode definition once the endorsement policy is satisfied.

B. Network Topology for COBALT

Based on the stakeholder model described in Section III, the Fabric network is instantiated with three organizations and three segregated channels to enforce data sovereignty.

1) *Organizational Structure*: The network comprises three primary organizations representing the key stakeholders in the certification ecosystem:

- **Org 1 (Manufacturer)**: submits design-time artifacts such as SBOMs and HBOMs.
- **Org 2 (Domain Operator)**: operates the certified systems and collects runtime evidence, including vulnerability reports.
- **Org 3 (Certification Authority)**: defines certification schemes and issues the final compliance verdicts.

2) *Channel Topology and Data Segregation*: To balance transparency with confidentiality, the network employs three segregated channels (see Fig. 2):

- **Artifact Channel (Manufacturer ↔ Operator)**: distributes product information. Manufacturers write artifacts; Operators have read-only access. Write control is enforced via chaincode-level MSP ID validation.

Fig. 2. Hyperledger Fabric architecture for COBALT.

- Certification Channel (CAB ↔ Manufacturer): the CAB publishes certification schemes and certificates; Manufacturers read them to demonstrate compliance.
- Vulnerability Channel (Operator ↔ CAB): Operators submit incident reports, which the CAB reads to assess potential certificate revocation.

C. Identity Management and Integration

1) *Identity Mapping Pattern*: COBALT employs an OpenID Connect (OIDC)-based Identity Manager for user authentication. The blockchain middleware maps authenticated OIDC tokens to local Fabric MSP identities (e.g., a “Manufacturer” login is mapped to Org1MSP credentials), ensuring cryptographic non-repudiation without requiring end-users to manage X.509 certificates.

2) *REST API Gateway*: A REST API abstracts the Fabric software development kit (SDK) complexity, handling the full transaction flow (Proposal, Endorsement, Ordering) and exposing simple Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) endpoints (e.g., POST /evidence, GET /certificate) for integration with heterogeneous COBALT components.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Automated Network Orchestration

The implementation was validated on the COBALT testbed: a Proxmox Virtual Environment (Proxmox VE) virtual machine running Ubuntu 22.04 LTS with 4 vCPU cores and 16 GB of RAM. The blockchain topology is containerized via Docker using Hyperledger Fabric v2.5 images with a Raft-based ordering service for crash fault tolerance (CFT).

The core of the automation is the `setup.sh` orchestration script, which transforms the declarative JSON definitions into a running network by dynamically iterating over the `organizations.json` array to:

- 1) *Generate Crypto-Material*. It bootstraps the Fabric CA servers and uses the `fabric-ca-client` to register and enroll all network identities, organizing the resulting certificates and private keys into distinct MSP directories for each peer and orderer organization.
- 2) *Synthesize Configuration*. It programmatically constructs the `configtx.yaml` profiles, ensuring that the `AnchorPeers` and policies match the generated crypto-material.
- 3) *Containerize Infrastructure*. It generates dedicated `docker-compose` files for each peer node, ensuring they mount their specific MSPs and connect to their dedicated CouchDB instances for state storage.

Crucially, the script automates the Fabric 2.x Chaincode Lifecycle. Instead of manual administrative intervention, the system automatically packages the Java chaincode, installs it on all targeted peers, approves the definition for each organization (handling the required endorsement policies), and commits the chaincode definition to the channel once the majority consensus is reached.

B. Smart Contract Logic

The business logic is implemented in Java using the Fabric Contract API. To ensure data sovereignty, we strictly implement a “Hash-on-Chain” pattern. Listing 1 demonstrates the anchoring logic.

```

1 @Transaction(intent = Transaction.TYPE.SUBMIT)
2 public String putValue(final Context ctx, final String
   content) {
3     ChaincodeStub stub = ctx.getStub();
4
5     // 1. Deterministic Hashing (SHA-256)
6     // Computed on-chain to prevent hash manipulation
7     String hash = DigestUtils.sha256Hex(content);
8
9
10    // 2. Idempotency & Existence Check
11    if (!stub.getStringState(hash).isEmpty()) {
12        throw new ChaincodeException("Hash already exists")
13    };
14
15    // 3. Anchor with Immutable Metadata
16    Instant timestamp = ctx.getStub().getTxTimestamp();
17    String submitterMSP = ctx.getClientIdentity().getMSPID
18        ();
19
20    // Storing metadata allows for auditability
21    stub.putStringState(hash, submitterMSP + "::<" +
   timestamp.toString());
22    return hash;
23 }
  
```

Listing 1. Evidence anchoring function with in-contract hashing

This implementation enforces deterministic execution: hashing is performed inside the chaincode execution context on endorsing peers to ensure that all peers reach the same result, preventing “phantom reads” or non-deterministic consensus errors.

C. Integration Layer and API Gateway

Each stakeholder deploys its own Node.js API Gateway instance (using the `fabric-network` SDK) within its trust domain. The gateway implements the federated identity pattern described in Section IV: it maintains a server-side Wallet with

the organization’s X.509 credentials, validates incoming OIDC tokens, maps the user’s organization claim to the corresponding MSP identity, and signs transaction proposals accordingly. Although Fabric’s transaction flow is asynchronous (Submit → Order → Commit), the API blocks the HTTP response via `submitTransaction` until the transaction is committed, ensuring that a 200 OK guarantees ledger immutability. Endpoints are documented via OpenAPI/Swagger for seamless integration with COBALT’s dashboards and scanners.

VI. VALIDATION AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The automated deployment system was validated within the COBALT testbed, focusing on functional correctness of the evidence anchoring workflow and operational efficiency compared to manual deployment.

A. Functional Validation: Evidence Anchoring Workflow

To verify the integration between the COBALT ecosystem and the Hyperledger Fabric network, we simulated a complete certification lifecycle event: the submission of an SBOM by a Manufacturer.

The validation scenario proceeds as follows:

- 1) Submission. The Manufacturer’s system (via the CCM Manager) sends a JSON payload containing the SBOM to the REST API Gateway.
- 2) Anchoring. The API maps the request to the `Org1MSP` identity, invokes the smart contract to compute the SHA-256 hash, and commits the transaction to the `artifact` channel.
- 3) Verification. A third party (e.g., a CAB) queries the ledger to verify the existence and timestamp of the anchored evidence.

Listing 2 demonstrates the actual API interaction used in the testbed to anchor a CycloneDX SBOM.

```

1 # 1. Submit SBOM Evidence (Manufacturer)
2 $ curl -X POST http://cobalt-dlt:3000/v1/manufacturer/sbom
3 \
4 -H "Authorization: Bearer <OIDC_TOKEN>" \
5 -H "Content-Type: application/json" \
6 -d '{
7   "content": "{\"bomFormat\":\"CycloneDX\", ...}"
8 }'
9 # Response (201 Created):
10 { "hash": "e3b0c442..." }
11
12 # 2. Verify Existence and Retrieve Timestamp (CAB)
13 $ curl -X GET http://cobalt-dlt:3000/v1/manufacturer/sbom/
14 e3b0c442...
15 # Response (200 OK):
16 { "timestamp": "2026-02-08T10:00:00Z" }
```

Listing 2. REST API call to anchor a Manufacturer’s SBOM

The system successfully processed the transaction in the testbed environment, with an average end-to-end latency of 2.1 seconds (from HTTP request to block commitment).

B. Deployment Efficiency Analysis

We compared the deployment of the COBALT network topology (3 Organizations, 3 Channels, 3 Chaincodes) using our automated script versus manual configuration.

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF DEPLOYMENT METRICS

Metric	Manual Setup	Automated (Ours)
Config Files Edited	~12 (YAMLs)	3 (JSON)
Crypto-Material Gen.	Manual Steps	Auto-Generated
Deployment Time	~4-6 Hours	~3 Minutes
Human Error Risk	High	Minimal

As shown in Table I, the automated approach reduces the deployment time from hours to minutes. More importantly, it ensures cryptographic consistency across the network.

C. Resource Consumption

We monitored the resource usage of the full stack comprising 3 Peer nodes, 3 dedicated CouchDB instances, 1 Orderer node, 3 Certificate Authorities, and the API Gateway, all hosted on the 16 GB RAM / 4 vCPU virtual machine. The idling network consumes approximately 4.2 GB of RAM, leaving ample capacity for transaction processing. Under a load of continuous evidence submission (1 transaction/sec), central processing unit (CPU) usage remained below 15%, confirming that the containerized architecture is lightweight enough for the COBALT pilot infrastructure.

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presented a distributed trust infrastructure for continuous cybersecurity certification within the COBALT framework. To address the operational complexity of Hyperledger Fabric, we developed an infrastructure-as-code system that derives a fully operational network from three declarative JSON specifications, reducing deployment from hours to approximately three minutes. The resulting architecture enforces data sovereignty through segregated channels and a hash-on-chain anchoring pattern, while a federated identity mapping layer and a REST API gateway integrate the ledger with the broader COBALT ecosystem.

Validation confirmed the functional correctness of the evidence anchoring workflow (2.1 s average latency) and showed that the full containerized stack operates within modest resource constraints (4.2 GB RAM idle, below 15% CPU under continuous load). Although validated in a certification context, the framework applies to any consortium requiring permissioned ledgers without deep Fabric expertise.

A. Future Work

Two directions are planned:

- 1) *Context-Aware Content Validation*: Currently, the system anchors cryptographic proofs regardless of the underlying data structure. Future work will introduce a semantic validation layer that verifies off-chain data conforms to the required schemas (e.g., CycloneDX for SBOMs, OSCAL [11] for assessment reports) before committing hashes to the ledger. Additionally, a deterministic canonicalization step (e.g., JSON Canonicalization Scheme, RFC 8785) will be implemented to ensure semantically identical artifacts always produce the same SHA-256 fingerprint.

2) *Migration to Hyperledger Fabric 3.x*: The current implementation uses Fabric v2.5 with Raft (CFT) consensus, which tolerates crashed nodes but not malicious ones. Upgrading to Fabric 3.0 [12] with Byzantine fault tolerant (BFT) ordering would harden the infrastructure against compromised orderers.

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